

Transcendental Pluralism in Kant's Controversy with Forster about the Concept of Race¹

Patrícia Kauark-Leite

Federal University of Minas Gerais, BR

1. Introduction

In this essay, I critically reflect on Kant's view that there is not one single concept of nature, but instead a plurality of them, each correspondingly linked to different concepts of rationality. I will leave aside the most obvious distinction between (i) the concept of physical nature, characterized by causal determinism, and (ii) the concept of human nature, characterized by freedom, and focus only on distinctions related to physical nature as such. My task here is to analyze Kant's conceptual pluralism about nature and his corresponding conceptual pluralism about natural-scientific methods, from the perspective of the controversy between Kant and Forster about the concept of race.

Kant conceives of nature very differently from the classical empiricists, for whom nature is simply everything that exists outside of us. Unlike the empiricist perspective, in Kant's transcendental idealism, "nature" does not simply refer to the set of external objects, but more fundamentally to the fact that these objects have their existence concatenated according to necessary rules (CPR A216/B263). In §14 of the *Prolegomena to Any Future Metaphysics*, Kant defines nature as "the existence of things, insofar as that existence is determined according to universal laws" (Prol 4: 294). The existence of things is taken, evidently, in its empirical or material sense, not as the existence of things in themselves, but instead as the existence of the set of empirical objects that affect our sensibility. In the definition I just quoted from the *Prolegomena*, this intrinsic link between nature and law expresses the properly cognitive or epistemic dimension of Kant's concept of nature, not merely as something external that presents itself to us, but instead as something external that is also rationally conceived by us in the form of necessary laws. Kant argues that human understanding is the source of the general form of natural laws that structure all the material given objects of our experience. Nature is, therefore, in the Kantian perspective, conceived ultimately in an inherently relational way. as a product of our cognitive interaction with the world.

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However, in the very first paragraph of the Preface to the *Metaphysical Foundations of Natural Science*, Kant draws our attention to the plurality of ways in which nature can be thought under laws. He Writes:

There can be as many different natural sciences as there are specifically different things, each of which must contain its own peculiar inner principle of the determinations belonging to its existence. (*MNS* 4: 467).

Ahead of its time, Kant's philosophy of science is committed not only to ontological pluralism, but also to methodological pluralism. From this perspective we can assert that there is no single overarching scientific method, but instead a plurality of methods, each according to the plurality of kinds of nature.

With regard to external sensible objects, Kant considers at least two very different types of law-governedness, and, therefore, two very different types of scientific rationality for the natural world, that correspondingly imply two very different concepts of physical nature. On the one hand, he considers a mechanical or physical rationality, construed in terms of necessary and universal principles or laws of nature, whose foundations are laid out in the *Transcendental Analytic* of the *Critique of Pure Reason*. But on the other hand, he also considers a teleological rationality that is needed in order to investigate biological life and organic objects, which cannot be rationally supported by mechanical laws based on the idea of efficient causality. In this sense, reason cannot limit itself to the sphere of the principles of the faculty of understanding. It is therefore necessary to hypothesize another kind of rationality, based on a distinct law-governedness, suitable for scientifically thinking about the objects of biology, which include living organisms and organized beings in general. This is what Kant presents to us in the second part of the *Critique of the Power of Judgment*, where he describes the teleological principle of purposiveness of nature as categorically distinct from the principle of mechanical causality.

I've already explored the distinction between mechanical rationality and biological rationality in another essay (Kauark-Leite, 2012). Here, I want to emphasise that Kant postulates different scientific rationalities even in the field of biological sciences, in his different attempts to classify and explain living beings. In order to clarify the methodological differences in the biological domain, I will base my comments on Kant's 1788 essay, "Concerning the Use of Teleological Principles in Philosophy" (*ETP* 8: 157-184). It is most often referred to as the third of Kant's trilogy on race, in which he addresses the old question of diversity among members of the human species. Given the importance that Kant ascribes to teleology in his natural history and also to the question of the origin of human diversity, John Zammito argues that Kant's theory of race is not a mere

appendix to his philosophy of science, that could be discarded without affecting its content; on the contrary, according to him, the 1788 essay represents “some of the most important writing Kant ever did on the methodology of science” (Zammito, 1992: pp. 200, 208). Indeed, this essay led Kant to the transcendental grounding of teleological principles in nature that is so crucial to his third *Critique*.

In this programmatic 1788 essay, Kant responds to the objections raised by the German naturalist and ethnographer George Forster (1754-1794) against Kant’s methodological proposal to make use of teleological principles in order to explain variations in the human species. In what follows, I’ll critically explore the theme of methodological plurality in natural science, as it arises in the controversy between Kant and Forster about the concept of race. In my opinion, they are representatives of very different scientific research programs, whose clash still finds resonance nowadays in the contemporary debates about scientific methodology. My goal is also to deepen our understanding of the place of empirical observation in Kant’s theory of knowledge of living beings.

2. Forster and His Objections

Georg Forster, a naturalist, accompanied his father Johann Reinhold Forster, also a naturalist, on several scientific expeditions. The younger Forster is also generally regarded as one of the founders of modern travel literature. His account of his voyage with the British navigator and cartographer James Cook, to the Pacific Ocean, in two volumes, entitled *A Voyage Round the World* (Forster, 1777/2000), made him famous, and also significantly contributed to the ethnological study of the people of Polynesia. By contrast with Kant, who never left either his homeland or the city he grew up in, Königsburg, Forster was a naturalist not just in theory but in practice. Forster reported what he actually observed; and he also naively believed that he had no philosophical beliefs in addition to or presupposed by his descriptions. In my opinion, however, he held or presupposed at least one basic philosophical belief: namely, that his observations were theoretically neutral. On the other hand, always sitting in his armchair, Kant read and studied travellers’ reports and imaginatively ventured entered into the domains of ethnology, anthropology, and physical geography, but without taking a single trip.

Instead of discussing the differences between Kant’s and Forster’s concepts of human diversity and races, I want to explore their methodological differences. The dispute between them originates with Forster’s essay, “Something More about the Human Races,” published in 1786 in the Enlightenment magazine, *Der teutsche Merkur*. In this essay, he criticizes—with

much irony directed at Kant's armchair speculations—two writings by Kant: “Determination of the Concept of a Human Race” (*HR* 8: 89-106) from 1785, and “Conjectural Beginning of Human History” (*CBHH* 8: 125-130) from 1786.

Forster begins his critique by calling our attention to the balance that must exist between the faculty of abstraction and the faculty of intuition. The emphasis on just one of these cognitive structures to the detriment of the another prejudices the Enlightenment project of advancing knowledge. According to Forster, one-sidedness must be avoided at all costs. And indeed, it's one-sidedness that Forster he identifies as the characteristic feature of Kant's pseudo-scientific adventure in the field of natural history. According to Forster, a real-world naturalist, Kant ignores actual experience when discusses the concept of race for the purposes of his classification of human diversity. Forster stresses that empirical data, if not correctly interpreted, pave the way for utterly absurd and empty reasoning.

Forster also points out that the natural classification system proposed by Linnaeus is far from being perfect and must continually be adjusted in the face of new discoveries. As scientific research advances and our vision broadens, what initially seemed to us to be true conceptual determinations, become at most partially true and even false. Forster goes so far as to conjecture that even philosophical systems, as in the case of the *Critique of Pure Reason*, may have a fate similar to that of all empirical systems for classifying beings in nature: namely, eventually becoming historically obsolete.

Moreover, Forster warns readers about possible misunderstandings and misuses of the claim made by Kant right at the beginning of “Determination of a Concept of a Human Race”: one finds in experience what one needs only if one knows in advance what to look for” (*HR* 8: 91). For Forster, it is necessary to be careful not to fall into the most common of illusions: that of believing to have found what is really not present, when one looks only for what is needed in order to confirm one's beliefs, an illusion nowadays known as *confirmation bias*. The observer who starts from unquestionable definitions, due to his partisan project of systematizing experiential data, often runs the risk of seeing many things in a distorted or even outright false way, thereby deceiving himself and others. If he avails himself of a defective and partial principle, his vision of objects will be distorted and unreliable. In Forster's words: he “lends the color of his glasses to the objects.” The empiricist naturalist traveller, Forster, explicitly opposing himself to the rationalistic speculative philosopher, Kant, engages in an enthusiastic defence of the impartial observer who “only faithfully and reliably reports what he perceives without pondering for a long time which speculative theory [*Spekulation*] his perception favours” (Forster, 1786/2013: p. 148). And in the comparison between the empiricist method and the speculative systematic

method, there would be more truth, according to Forster, in the similar reports of different travellers, who, despite their theoretical orientations, were to agree in the presentation of what was actually observed.

Forster argues that in order to observe the color of an object or of a human being, it doesn't matter whether the observer knows optical theory or not. The most relevant fact, for the naturalist, is the agreement between the observers, attributing the same color to what they observe. His aim in this argument is to criticize Kant's doctrine about attributing a determinate primary or true color to a certain groups of people. He criticizes in particular Kant's assertion that a determinate primary color could not be attributed with certainty to the population of the islands of the South Pacific, based on traveller reports. Forster suggests that the Kant's confusion comes first from those who try to generalize what is only valid for a small observed region. Many mistakes are made when the diversity and nuances of hues are not considered in favour of the search for a primary or true color. He objects that perhaps the distinctive sign selected by Kant to define race is poorly chosen and questionable. He accuses Kant of confusing concepts or hypotheses "constructed from a matter of fact" with "the matter of fact itself" (Forster, 1786/2013: p. 157). According to the naturalist, we are led to absurd inconsistencies when we impose conceptual divisions on nature that do not follow their own order. Against Kant and his speculative systematizing, Forster defends an empirical naturalism, contesting the very idea of any conceptual order that comes to superimpose itself on the natural order. He also criticizes Kant's idea of a natural history that seeks to determine the origin of differentiations in the species. In Forster's words:

If, however, the differences can no longer be traced historically back to their point of origination, then the least that we can do is regard the descent as undetermined; and the distinction that Kant wants to make between the concepts [*Begriffen*] of the description of nature and the knowledge of natural history must become altogether void. (1786/2013: p. 164)

3. Kant's Response to Forster's Objections

Kant's response to Forster's objections, in defence of his speculative systematizing about race, was not long in coming. In 1788 and in the same magazine in which Forster published his objections, *Der teutsche Merkur*, Kant's reply appeared under the title, "Concerning the Use of Teleological Principles in Philosophy" (ETP 8: 157-184). In it, Kant develops his distinction between *natural description* and *natural history*, mentioned in a footnote in his 1785 essay, "Determination of the Concept of a Human Race" (HR 8: 89-106), and also summarized in the Preface of his 1786 book, *Metaphysical Foundations of Natural Science* (MNS 4: 465-565). Kant defines *natural description* "as a system of

classification for natural things in accordance with their similarities,” and *natural history* “as a systematic presentation of natural things at various times and places” (MNS 4: 468). These two strands of the *historical doctrine of nature* are both characterized by being empirical and historical, and thereby distinguish themselves from physics, which is a non-empirical, rational science of nature. Thus, in the realm of the natural sciences, Kant distinguishes between rational knowledge (*cognitio ex principiis*) and historical knowledge (*cognitio ex datis*) (cf. CPR A836/B 864; JL 9: 22), and in turn, the latter is subdivided into natural description and natural history. Kant had in mind specifically the work of Carl Linnaeus (1707-1778), who classified the genera and species of animals, vegetables, and minerals, as the paradigmatic example of natural description, by contrast with works of natural history carried out by contemporary naturalists, for example: G-L.L. Buffon (1707-1788), Konrad Mannert (1756–1834), Jean-Baptiste Bourguignon D’Anville (1697–1782), Edme Mentelle (1730–1815), Anton Friedrich Büsching (1724–93), Christof Daniel Ebeling (1741–1817), Ferdinand Gottlieb Canzler (1764–1813), August Friedrich Wilhelm Crome (1753–1833) and Christian Friedrich Ludwig (1751–1823). All of these naturalists are cited by Kant himself in his course on *Physical Geography* (PG 9: 159-163, 213, 303), published in 1802. Buffon’s massive work on natural history, produced over a period of forty years and comprising 36 volumes, *Histoire naturelle générale et particulière* (Buffon, 1774), is the paradigmatic example of “a systematic presentation [of the facts concerning natural things] at various times and places.” Nevertheless, Linnaeus’s *Systema naturae*, published in 1758, unlike the works of Buffon and other natural historians, presents us with a classification system in which experience is articulated according to logical criteria of connections between different concepts (PG 9: 159-160). Linnaeus’s work is therefore not a geographical or historical description, but instead a logical description of nature, namely a logical system of natural classification.

In *Physical Geography*, Kant calls our attention to the fact that the term “natural history” is often incorrectly used by most natural scientists (PG 9: 161-162). Under the heading of “natural history,” they are really presenting us with what is strictly speaking neither a natural history, nor a narrative about origins, nor a system of nature, as we find it in Linnaeus, but instead a geographical description of nature. Physical geography and natural history are distinguished by reference to events, whether in their relationships in space, as in the former, or in their relationships in time, as in the latter. Systematic presentations of natural facts, contained in geographical descriptions, are more accurately characterized as “aggregations of nature” (*Aggregate der Natur*) than as a “system of Nature” (*Systema Naturae*), because they do not contain the idea of a systematic whole (PG 9: 160). Kant makes use here of the methodological distinction he had established in the Architectonic of Pure Reason of the first *Critique* between aggregate and system. According to him, in the text of Architectonic, it is the

notion of systematic unity that properly transforms the ordinary empirical cognition into scientific knowledge. He defines the notion of a system as “the unity of the manifold cognitions under one idea” (CPR A832/B860). And whatever that idea is, it is based on the transcendental principle of purposiveness.² Although it is in the Critique of Teleological Power of Judgment, that Kant will defend the autonomy of teleological judgment to think about living organisms.

However, in “Concerning the Employment of Teleological Principles in Philosophy,” Kant makes progress in relation to his previous conceptualisations in the *Metaphysical Foundations of Natural Science*, in the defence of a proper epistemic place for natural history. This place is identified neither with the logical classification of nature, as in the Linnaean system, nor with physical descriptions as aggregates of nature. In the face of Forster’s objections against the limitation of historical investigation, Kant wants to argue positively in favor of legitimate narratives about the origins of natural species. In opposition to the naturalist, Kant advocates the use of metaphysical principles as a resource to explain what empirical investigation is not able to offer. And since natural organisms cannot be explained by means of mathematical-mechanical laws, it is necessary to resort to principles of a teleological nature in order to explain and unify the data collected by empirical investigation. Therefore, against Forster’s naturalist program, Kant counterargues that experience by itself is not enough to provide an explanation of nature, especially of the origin of organic beings. However, even admitting that such an undertaking might be based on a variety of hypotheses, hence epistemically risky, it is still necessary to accept that risk. A natural history based only on empirically observable features, without hypothetically conjecturing about the conditions that led to the present state of affairs is, in Kant’s words, like “mere empirical groping without a guiding principle of what to search for” (ETP 8: 161).

Kant begins “Concerning the Employment of Teleological Principles in Philosophy” by reaffirming his concept of nature as “the sum-total of all that exists as determined by laws” (ETP 8: 159). In the search for laws, two paths of investigating nature are possible: the theoretical or the teleological. In metaphysics, as he demonstrated in the Dialectic of Pure Reason in the *Critique of Pure Reason*, by showing the impossibility of having theoretical knowledge of transcendent objects, only the teleological path is possible. But in physics, both paths are possible. We follow the theoretical path as far as possible, but wherever that path ends, we are left with only the teleological path. Indeed, in

² For a discussion of the Kantian distinction between aggregate and system, and also for a better understanding of the notion of purposiveness as a design or as a normativity, see (Ypi, 2021: esp. ch. 3).

“Determination of the Concept of a Human Race,” he tried to prove just that, with respect to human races, namely, that there is “a need to start from a teleological principle where theory abandons us” (ETP 8: 159).

However, caution should be exercised. Teleology can never make up for the lack of theoretical investigation. Only reluctantly and with due resistance, does the theoretical understanding submit to teleological reason. In all investigation of nature, one appeals first to theory, and then only later to teleology, and even then, as Kant puts it, “the right of *precedence* of the theoretical-speculative investigation” (ETP 8: 160) should always be conceded. Within the scope of teleological investigation, consensus about principles is difficult to agree on. Misunderstandings result from the fact that they concern the method of *thinking* about objects and not the method of determining objects. This results in a significant tension in relation to the two aims of reason, which are here in conflict with each other: (i) the theoretical aim, limited to sensible intuition and mechanical causality, and (ii) the teleological aim, guided by the search for a final causality, thereby expanding the reach of reason beyond the limits imposed by spatiotemporal intuition. This is also a tension about the scope of reason’s operations. On the one hand, reason must operate autonomously. But on the other hand, reason must restrict its operations to empirically conditioned objects.

Faced with this tension, Kant tries to respond to Forster’s objections to the idea that a teleological principle can guide natural-scientific research and empirical observations and to the possibility of rigorously developing a natural history. From the empirical naturalist’s perspective, only gods that were present at the moment of creation would have been able to observe the emergence of species. Forster therefore criticizes the distinction postulated by Kant between natural description and natural history. Forster argues that only the first one, which seeks to classify natural species and not explain their origin and descent, is scientifically possible. Kant defends his distinction by counterarguing that part of the misunderstanding contained in Forster’s criticism is due to the fact that he does not consider that both enterprises—natural description and natural history—are sciences with very different methodologies and approaches. Thus, according to Kant, it would be a mistake to impose on natural history (better labelled as a *physiogony*) the same empirical method of investigation as the natural description (better labelled as a *physiography*) (ETP 8: 163n). In *physiogony*, unlike empirical investigation, reason has the methodological task of providing a teleological principle that explores and explains the diversity that we find in empirical research in the absence of observable data. In natural history, it is not a case of seeking narratives of natural events from a divine point of view beyond human reason, but instead a case of sifting and sorting empirical data by means of conjectures, in a game whose players are imagination, understanding, and reason. So, in Kant’s words:

Yet *natural history* would only consist in tracing back, as far as the analogy permits, the connection between certain present-day conditions of the things in nature and their causes in earlier times according to laws of efficient causality, which we do not make up but derive from the powers of nature as it presents itself to us now. (ETP 8: 161-162)

It's important to note that in this essay, Kant is using an *epistemic* and not an *ontological* argument in order to defend his concept of the human race against the Forster's criticism that it lacks an empirical basis. According to Kant, what determines the variety of races is only the empirical constancy or inconstancy of its characteristics. For example, let's say that empirical investigation was able to prove that a family of black-skinned people can lose its color, after several generations, when changing regions. This confirms that they're a human race, because their characteristics would be changeable due to purely climatic or geographic reasons. Kant, correspondingly, argues in favor of the concept of race *not* as an essential characteristic of nature, but only as a heuristic concept, introduced by reason, to explain original characteristics of a common stock of the human species. Its importance is restricted to the scope of natural history. It is totally dispensable for the system of description of nature, where the concept of contingent variety is sufficient to classify diversity. From the the fact of this concept does not figure among those of the description of nature, it does not follow that it is also unsuitable for natural history. If on the one hand, the concept of variety is essential for the description of nature in order to explain the differences, nevertheless, on the other hand, the concept of race in natural history fulfills a key role in "indicating a common phyletic origination" (ETP 8: 163). It allows us to identify several original characters that persist from generation to generation.

For Kant, in a system of natural history, the concept of a *human species*, also present by means of natural description, could be divided into three other concepts: *phylum*, *race*, and *human sort* or *variety* (ETP 8: 164). Since this third one does not infallibly reproduce a classifiable hereditary characteristic, it does not serve as a justification for classifying diversity of *human species*. Race, in its turn, authorises the division into classes because it is a hereditarily enduring variety. Variety is a concept that was given to nature by reason in order to assign a greater multiplicity for the benefit of a variety of ends. Likewise, race would also be given to nature by reason with the goal of unifying multiplicity in accordance with a reduced number of more essential ends. However, from a methodological point of view, it is necessary to bear in mind that all this conceptual division

is so far merely an idea of the way in which the greatest degree of manifoldness in the generation can be united by reason with the greatest unity of phyletic origin. (ETP 08: 164)

It is thus a purely artificial and methodological nomenclature, introduced by reason in order to serve as a guide for observation. Kant thus clearly distances himself, in the context of the historical doctrines of nature, both from an empirical naturalism and from an essentialist realism, thereby moving much closer to a conventionalist philosophy of science as it emerged at the end of the 19th century.

Moreover, the concept of race performs an explanatory causal function not in terms of efficient or mechanical causality, but only in terms of final or teleological causality. In Kant's words:

Since the concept of an organized being already includes that it is some matter in which everything is mutually related to each other as end and means, which can only be thought as a *system of final causes*, and since therefore their possibility only leaves the teleological but not the physical-mechanical mode of explanation, at least as far as *human* reason is concerned, there can be no investigation in physics about the origin of all organization itself. (*ETP* 8: 179).

In this sense, the concept of race, which has a causal function of explaining the human diversity, is, for Kant, a merely *regulative* idea, and not *constitutive* of experience as it would be via physical-mechanical causality. By virtue of the principle of sufficient reason, we are led to think that everything in nature — including organisms, animals, and human beings — has an explanation. However, the mechanical principles of nature are not able to provide a human knowledge of natural organisms, much less explain them. Therefore, it is necessary to expand the scope of the principle of sufficient reason beyond the principle of mechanical causality or the Second Analogy of Experience in the first *Critique*. The causal rule, established by the understanding, of the objective succession of all changes in time is not sufficient to make the systematic unity required by reason possible. The role of the Transcendental Analytic in the first *Critique* was to establish the *a priori* conditions for a concept of objective nature in general. At this level, the contingent, singular, intuitable, and spatiotemporal events are ordered and synthesized by the understanding that attributes causal determinism to them. What transcends the scope of the Transcendental Analytic is the explanation of “internal possibility,” not just of the series of events and empirical facts, but also of nature as a whole. Since the Transcendental Deduction of the categories and the derivation of the principles of pure understanding do not provide sufficient transcendental conditions to account for the organisation and systematic character of nature, Kant finds himself compelled, above all by his investigations in natural history, to expand transcendental reflection beyond the constitutive principles of experience. In this sense, “Concerning the Employment of Teleological Principles in Philosophy” is a foreshadowing of the view he would present and defend two years later in his *Critique of the Power of Judgment*.

4. Conclusion

It is crucial to recognize that, in this expanded version of the principle of sufficient reason, including but not restricted to the principle of efficient causality, the concept of race, in its role of teleological explanation, does not have *constitutive* epistemic force, but instead only *regulative* epistemic force. However, it is a necessarily true counterfactual for Kant that, if teleological principles *were* constitutive, then they *would* provide an objective explanation of organisms as things in themselves. From this perspective, the concept of race would be an essential and intrinsic characteristic of human beings. But Kant refuses to consider race in this way. He places it in the teleological causal domain, not in the mechanical-deterministic causal domain. Its role is only regulative, but no less fundamental in an epistemic sense. Only reason is capable of offering a set of principles or maxims that, once introduced into our cognitive dynamics, produce a theoretical unity, from which the notion of the objective purpose of nature derives. Joãozinho Beckenkamp thus aptly refers to Kant's teleology by using the term "analogical teleology," as opposed to what Beckenkamp calls "attributive teleology," i.e., the "attribution of ends and designs to nature" (Beckenkamp, 2017: p. 331). In other words, Kant's teleology is an exercise in thinking by analogy (cf. Beckenkamp, 2008).

In this analogical sense, "Concerning the Employment of Teleological Principles in Philosophy" is insightful in its theoretical move of expanding the principle of sufficient reason. The identification of the principle of sufficient reason with that of mechanical-deterministic causality for the determination of an objective chronological order of objects of perception has its validity limited to the level of understanding. Nevertheless, reason demands more. It demands that the sufficiency of natural-scientific explanation must be sought in the idea of the complete unity of the concepts of understanding, even though this is only possible hypothetically or counterfactually. In order to arrive at the conception of an organized system, whether from the point of view of natural description or of natural history, one cannot fail to appeal to regulative teleological ideas. Kant mentions several of them in the first Introduction to the third *Critique*: "nature takes the shortest route – she does nothing in vain – she makes no leaps in the manifold of forms (*continuum formarum*) – she is rich in species but sparing with genera, etc." Kant points out that these formulas

are nothing other than this very same transcendental expression of the power of judgment in establishing a principle for experience as a system and hence for its own needs. (*FICPJ* 20: 210)

The same is true for Kant of the concept of race, which, strictly speaking, is neither true nor false, and therefore is not factually descriptive of physical nature but instead only prescriptive of the diversity of human animals.

The concepts or ideas of reason, though not directly and constitutively applicable to any object of empirical intuition, have an entirely legitimate and absolutely indispensable regulative use for completing the task of understanding. While understanding aims to unify the manifold of experience through its concepts, reason aims to unify all empirical regularities through its ideas, and seeks the maximum possible expansion of our representation of the world of actual and possible experience. If we lose our critical perspective and mistakenly assign a real ontological import to the ideas of reason—for instance, in the case of the concept of race—then we fall into insoluble paradoxes.

For my purposes in this essay, what is of interest in the controversy between Forster and Kant about the concept of race is the clash between two programs of scientific investigation: one, radically empiricist and in favor of the uniqueness of the scientific method, based on empirical observation, and another that defends methodological plurality and the inclusion of metaphysical ideas that guide and give meaning to experience. Sally Gray, who wrote an important article on this controversy, assumes that modern natural science has proved Forster right and not Kant. As she puts it: “Clearly Forster’s rejection of Kant’s introduction of metaphysics into empirical science is more in line with modern scientific theory” (Gray, 2012: p. 404). But I’m defending the opposite approach. The nature of natural science, in my opinion, is far more adequately captured by Kant’s philosophy of science than by Forster’s implicit empiricist naturalism. The idea of the uniqueness of the scientific method and the elimination of metaphysics from all scientific investigation, typical of the Logical Positivist or Logical Empiricist conception of science that is characteristic of the Vienna Circle, has been clearly rejected by post-Positivist and contemporary philosophy of science. In this sense, I believe that Kant anticipated by at least two hundred years some of the well-known doctrines of Paul Feyerabend and Thomas Kuhn, for whom scientific observation is always metaphysically “theory-laden” and “ontologically committed,” about methodological and ontological pluralism.

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